

CONCENTRATION OF ASCORBIGEN FROM CABBAGE.

BY BAIDYANATH GHOSH AND B. C. GUHA.

Ascorbigen (combined ascorbic acid) has been concentrated from cabbage juice by adsorption with "active" charcoal and by elution with a chloroform-alcohol mixture. Some of the properties of the ascorbigen concentrate are described.

In preceding papers (Pal and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 481; Sen-Gupta and Guha, *ibid.*, p 496) cabbage has been shown to contain ascorbigen (or combined ascorbic acid) by both chemical and biological methods. It was shown further that chloroform extracts of dried cabbage contained ascorbigen and some other non-specific reducing substances in a combined state but no free ascorbic acid. Although evaporating off the solvent from the chloroform extract and taking up the residue in water followed by centrifugation produced a considerable concentration of the ascorbigen of the chloroform extract, the yield of ascorbigen so far as the fresh cabbage was concerned was not satisfactory, as chloroform did not extract all the ascorbigen of cabbage (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *loc. cit.*)

In subsequent experiments we have started with cabbage juice. Glacial metaphosphoric acid produced a precipitate, but it was found that by this means only a fraction of ascorbigen could be precipitated along with some proteins and the main bulk of ascorbigen remained in the filtrate. Similar observations have been made by Scarborough and Stewart (*Nature*, 1938, **142**, 40). In order to precipitate ascorbigen completely from the cabbage juice different protein precipitating reagents were employed without success.

The next attempt was to concentrate ascorbigen from the cabbage juice by suitable adsorbing materials. Fuller's earth, charcoal ("Norit") and active charcoal (Schering-Kahlbaum, "carbo-active") were employed and it was found that charcoal could adsorb the largest amount of ascorbigen from the cabbage juice. The concentration of ascorbigen by charcoal adsorption and subsequent elution by suitable solvents is described in this paper. Further work on the nature of ascorbigen so eluted and its further purification is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Separation of Ascorbigen from Cabbage Juice by Glacial Metaphosphoric Acid.

Fresh cabbage (1 kg.) was minced in a hand mincer and cabbage juice was pressed out by pressing in a screw-press. The juice obtained measured

500 c.c. Water (100 c.c.) was then added to the pressed cabbage pulp and a further yield of the cabbage juice was thus obtained. The total volume of the juice expressed measured 600 c.c. This was centrifuged in order to remove insoluble matter. Glacial metaphosphoric acid was added to the clear juice so as to make the acid concentration 5%. The precipitate obtained after adding glacial metaphosphoric acid weighed 9 g. (moist). About 0.5 g. of this precipitate was suspended in 15 c.c. of distilled water. 10 C.c. of this suspension were centrifuged and the clear liquid obtained titrated with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 30) in order to estimate the free reducing substance present. No reduction of the dye was observed. The remaining 5 c.c. of the suspension were made up to 10 c.c. by the addition of distilled water and this suspension was heated on a water-bath in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide for 10 minutes. The suspension was then cooled under water while carbon dioxide was allowed to bubble. It was then centrifuged and the clear liquid after making up to 10 c.c. was titrated with the dye as usual. The amount of reducing substance liberated by heat treatment, when calculated as ascorbic acid, was found to be 0.312 mg. of ascorbic acid per 0.5 g. of the metaphosphoric acid precipitate. Thus the total 9 g. precipitate contained about 5.6 mg. of ascorbic acid in a combined state.

The filtrate remaining after glacial metaphosphoric acid precipitation when similarly heated for 10 minutes in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide released a considerable amount of reducing substances. The amount of ascorbigen remaining in the centrifugate when expressed in terms of ascorbic acid was found to be 29 mg., showing that the larger proportion of ascorbigen was not precipitated by metaphosphoric acid under our conditions of experiment.

Different Protein-precipitating Reagents and Ascorbigen Concentration.

Since a considerable amount of ascorbigen remained in the filtrate after metaphosphoric acid precipitation it was considered desirable to study the behaviour of different protein-precipitating reagents like trichloroacetic acid, ammonium sulphate, alcohol, etc., with regard to the complete precipitation of ascorbigen from pressed cabbage juice. Different aliquots of juice were taken and different protein precipitating reagents employed. A portion of the filtrate after the separation of the protein was directly titrated with the dye while another portion was heated in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide on a boiling water-bath for 10 minutes. The difference

between these two values gave the amount of reducing substance expressed in terms of ascorbic acid present in the filtrate as ascorbigen. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Figures are given for 100 c.c. of cabbage juice.

No. of expt.	Reagents employed (giving final concentrations).	Ascorbic acid in the filtrate.		Ascorbigen present in the filtrate in terms of ascorbic acid.
		Initially present.	Obtained after heat treatment.	
1	Juice alone	0.57 mg.	4.3 mg.	3.73 mg.
2	5% CCl_3COOH	0.57	3.7	3.13
3	<i>m</i> - HPO_3 (5%)	0.67	4.3	3.65
4	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (40%)	0.43	4.3	3.87
5	Alcohol (50%)	0.52	3.4	2.88
6	HCl (5%)	0.52	4.0	3.48

It was thus observed that in all cases most of the ascorbigen remained in the filtrate and the method of precipitating ascorbigen by these protein-precipitating reagents was, therefore, discarded. Lead acetate and basic lead acetate were also tried but were found largely ineffective in precipitating ascorbigen.

Adsorption Methods.

Since the main bulk of ascorbigen remained in the solution after treatment with protein-precipitating reagents, a suitable method of adsorbing ascorbigen was sought. Among the different materials employed, fuller's earth, "norite" charcoal and "active" charcoal (Schering-Kahlbaum, "carbo-active"), the last was found to be the best, norite charcoal almost equally good and fuller's earth (at p_H 6.2) was ineffective. It was found that by charcoal adsorption about 60% of ascorbigen in the cabbage juice could be adsorbed. When cabbage juice was shaken in a mechanical shaker for 1-1½ hours with charcoal (1.15 g. per 100 c.c. of cabbage juice) the ascorbigen was adsorbed on the charcoal. The amount of ascorbigen adsorbed by charcoal could be estimated by the difference in dye value obtained before and after charcoal adsorption by the usual method of heat treatment in

carbon dioxide. In order to obtain maximum adsorption, adsorption at different p_H values was tried and the results are tabulated in Table II. The choice of variation of p_H is limited as both at low and high p_H values ascorbigen is unstable.

TABLE II.

No. of expt.	p_H .	Amount of ascorbigen in terms of ascorbic acid present per 100 c.c. of cabbage juice	
		Before charcoal adsorption.	After charcoal adsorption.
1	6.2	2.7 mg.	0.94 mg.
2	6.4	2.7	0.96
3	6.8	2.3	0.86
4	5.0	1.8	0.90
5	4.0	1.8	0.65

Elution of Ascorbigen from the Charcoal Adsorbate.

The next problem was to elute the ascorbigen from the charcoal adsorbate without the ascorbigen being split up. It was found that ascorbigen could be eluted practically in tact but not quantitatively if the pressed moist charcoal adsorbate was heated under reflux with a mixture of 30% chloroform and 70% absolute alcohol. For every 10 g. of charcoal used 100 c.c. of the chloroform-alcohol mixture were employed. The whole charcoal adsorbate was taken in a round-bottomed flask, chloroform-alcohol mixture was added and the mixture heated under reflux on a water-bath at a temperature of 70-80° for 1 hour, after which the charcoal was filtered under suction. The filtrate contained ascorbigen, which could be concentrated under reduced pressure at ordinary temperature (30°). As soon as chloroform was evaporated a precipitate was obtained which contained very little ascorbigen and was, therefore, discarded after centrifuging. The remaining alcoholic extract was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator. The whole chloroform-alcohol extract may also be directly evaporated over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. A second extraction of the charcoal adsorbate gave a further yield of ascorbigen.

Further Purification and Properties of the Ascorbigen Preparation.

The pasty mass left after alcohol-chloroform evaporation contained ascorbic acid in the combined form associated with other materials.

Purification could be effected by dissolving this crude ascorbigen preparation in a minimum quantity of water, centrifuging off the precipitate and evaporating the centrifugate to dryness over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. The mass (A), thus obtained, is soluble in water and brown in colour. The p_H of the aqueous solution varied from 3.5 to 5.0 and it contained a small amount of free ascorbic acid. A considerable increase in dye value was obtained when the water extract was heated on a water-bath for 10 minutes in carbon dioxide atmosphere. In order to identify the released reducing substances, this material was subjected to the action of ascorbic acid oxidase, as described by Sen-Gupta and Guha (*loc. cit.*). It was found that the crude ascorbigen preparation (A), corresponding to 1 kg. (roughly) of fresh cabbage, contained 7.43 mg. of reducing substances in combined state, of which non-specific reducing substances, estimated by the oxidase method, amounted to 3 mg. Therefore, ascorbic acid actually present in the combined state amounted to 4.43 mg. Thus about 40% of the reducing material was derived from a non-ascorbic acid complex. Further purification of the crude ascorbigen preparation (A) is in progress. The ascorbigen in preparation (A) was non-dialysable through parchment or cellophane membrane. When an electric current was allowed to pass through the ascorbigen solution using different membranes and at different p_H values no better concentration of ascorbigen was obtained. At low p_H values ascorbigen was slowly split up.

The elements detected by sodium fusion showed the presence of nitrogen and sulphur and no phosphorus in preparation (A). Nitrogen present varied from 11 to 13%. Preparation (A) did not respond to the xanthoproteic, biuret and Millon's tests. It gave positive glyoxylic acid and Pauly reactions. It reduced Fehling's solution and gave a very strong Molisch's test.

The yields of ascorbigen preparation (A) from cabbage were naturally different from different cabbage samples and varied from 0.7 g. to 1.5 g. per kg. of fresh cabbage, which gave yields of juice varying from 600 to 1000 c.c. by our method of extraction. 0.7-1.5 G. of ascorbigen preparation (A) contained 7-13 mg. of reducing substances in the combined state, of which about 40% consisted of non-specific reducing substances.

Further Concentration of Ascorbigen Preparation (A).

A partial purification was effected by tungstic acid precipitation. The ascorbigen preparation (A) containing 2.8 mg. reducing substances in the combined state was dissolved in a minimum quantity of water and centrifuged. The centrifugate was treated with 2 c.c. of 5% sodium tungstate.

Sulphuric acid (3 c.c. of 1.3 *N*) was then slowly added and the mixture was centrifuged. Excess of sulphuric acid was quickly removed from the centrifugate by baryta till the p_H was brought near 6.2, and excess of barium, if any, was removed by CO_2 . Alternatively, excess of sulphuric acid was removed by solid barium carbonate. The clear liquid obtained by centrifugation contained practically all the original ascorbigen present in preparation (A) and, on evaporation in a vacuum desiccator, gave a highly hygroscopic brownish mass. This also gave a strong Molisch's reaction.

C O N C L U S I O N

Different protein-precipitating reagents were used for the concentration of ascorbigen from cabbage juice. Most of the ascorbigen, however, was obtained in the filtrate.

"Norite" charcoal and "active" charcoal (Schering-Kahlbaum, "carbo-active") were found to adsorb 60% of ascorbigen from fresh cabbage juice. Ascorbigen can be eluted in a large measure from this adsorbate by a chloroform-alcohol mixture.

The ascorbigen preparation obtained by the charcoal adsorption method gave a strong Molisch's reaction and reduced Fehling's solution. It contained nitrogen and sulphur but no phosphorus. It did not give xanthoproteic, biuret and Millon's tests. It gave positive glyoxylic acid and Pauly reactions.

The ascorbigen preparation on being split up by heat gave reducing substances, 60% of which were oxidised by ascorbic acid oxidase. The rest consisted of non-specific reducing substances, which were also apparently present in a combined state in the ascorbigen preparation.

The ascorbigen preparation could be further concentrated by means of sodium tungstate and sulphuric acid. The active materials were not precipitated by these reagents but appeared quantitatively in the filtrate.

Our best thanks are due to the Indian Research Fund Association for financing the researches on ascorbic acid.